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NEWS MEDIA FRAMING AND THE COVERAGE OF BOKO-HARAM INSURGENCY IN THE NORTHEAST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: *This study on News Media Framing and the Coverage of Boko-Haram Insurgency in North-East Nigeria is a position paper set out to identify the pattern of frames adopted by Nigerian news media in the coverage of Boko Haram insurgency. Because since 2009 when the activities of the Boko Haram sect became pronounced in Nigeria, its activities have continued to dominate public discourse. To this end, the media at national and international fronts keyed into the reportage of the rebellious activities of this terror group. Through various strategies adopted by the sect, they carry out their nefarious activities which include: suicide bombings, massacre, abductions, and other deadly activities. The study established that Nigerian media dominantly use news frames: peace neutral and mixed frames. The successes, most of which were attributed to the way and manner in which media handles them. The study blamed the media on several occasions for flaming the conflict, particularly regarding the nature of their reportage. The study also addressed the critical question; that the Nigerian media can play a critical role in resolving and or addressing insurgency in Nigeria. Adopting the media framing theory, it, therefore, recommends the optimization of positive frames to promote the peace media initiative which forms the critical plank of positive media interventions.*

Keywords: News Media, Framing, Coverage and Insurgency.

Introduction

The Nigerian State is not new to violent insurgencies within its borders. It has been a state characterized by communal clashes, ethnic unrest, religious conflicts, and inter-tribal fights. Some of the reasons for pandemonium on many occasions have been linked to something as trivial as inter-communal land border disagreement or as critical as environmental pollution from oil mining activities, and government policies (Ademola, 2014). Other issues that have been fingered as causative factors of unrest hinges on the control of power, uneven development, unfavorable elections or

population census outcomes, and most predominantly, religious fanaticism.

Terrorism is not also a new phenomenon in world history. It has existed in every age, and important terrorist groups as the following may serve as prominent examples, Okoli (2017, p.42):

The Baader Meinhof gang of West Germany, the Japanese Red Army, the Italian Red Brigade, the Palestinian al-Fatah, the Israeli Haganah, the Lebanese Hezbollah, Osama Ibn Laden's Al-Qaeda, the Khmer Rouge of Cambodia, the Viet Cong in Vietnam, the Somalian al-Shabaab, Al-Qaeda in the Maghreb (AQIM) and

the Islamic State group (ISIS) in Iraq, Syria, Libya, Egypt and other parts of the world (for instance, Chad, Cameroon, and Nigeria). In Nigeria, Boko Haram has recently (2013) been listed by the United States among the league of the world's terrorist groups.

Terrorism, arguably, is one of the most serious threats contemporarily to global peace and stability. "...authoritative speaking, since the dawn of this millennium, the incidence of terrorism has been on a steady increase worldwide. Hitherto, however, terrorism was more or less a national or regional affair, Okoli (2017, p.39)". Some years ago, terrorism still seemed to be restricted to a few isolated places, such as Northern Ireland, the Basque Country in northern Spain, and some parts of the Middle East. Since 11 September 2001, with the destruction of the Twin Towers in New York – it has mushroomed into a worldwide phenomenon.

The scholars went on to point out that since Nigeria broke from the shackles of British colonial rule in 1960, the country has increasingly found it difficult to surmount its basic security challenges. Security and stability appear to have been the major challenges in the nation's political history (Okoli,2017), further argue that since independence, not a single decade has passed without at least one major cataclysmic crisis in Nigeria. For instance, Nigeria experienced the Western region political crises in the 1960s, incessant military coups, and a fratricidal civil war between 1967 and 1970. The last three to four decades also witnessed some of the worst civil and sectarian crises. Cases in point include the Maitatsine riots, starting in Kano and spreading to most parts of northern Nigeria in the 1980s, the

ethnoreligious crises in Kafanchan and ZangoKataf in Southern Kaduna in 1987 and 1992, the intractable ethnoreligious crisis in Jos since early 2000 to date, and 1993, 2007 and 2011 post-election crises that spread across the country, most especially the northern parts of Nigeria.

Although in the northern region entirely, religious-related violence to achieve some political or religious ends is certainly not a new phenomenon, the recent Boko – Haram uprising especially in the northeast has proved beyond reasonable doubt that it is the worse insurgence ever witnessed in the area. As noted above, the first involved the Maitatsine otherwise known as "Yan Tatsine" riot of December 1980, which claimed thousands of lives, this set the tones for subsequent riots involving the Maitatsine heretical anti-materialists Islamic sect in other Northeastern cities of Nigeria like Maiduguri-Bulunkutu, Yola-Jimeta and Gombe, followed by the 1987 and 1999 Kafanchan-Kaduna ethnoreligious riots which revived the old age tension between the Muslim Hausa-Fulani and non-Muslim community throughout the North and beyond (Hamida, 2014). Other major ones include the ZangonKataf riots of 1992, the Tafawa Balewa clashes of 1991, 1995, and 2000, the Kaduna riots of 2000, and the Jos crises of 2001 in which several hundreds of lives and properties were destroyed (Aduku, 2019). Sadly, these heinous activities the blood-sucking elements caused have to continue unabated and this has continued to dominate public discourse.

Conceptual Overview

This paper seeks to review the following concepts: News media, News framing, Reportage, and Insurgency.

News Media: According to (Shirley-Biagi, 2001), it comprises Television, Newspapers,

radio, and the Internet collectively: the various means of mass communication considered as a whole, including television, radio, magazines, and newspapers, together with the people involved in their production. Shirley further defined media as a human companion, it is enshrined into the daily life of every human breathing under the sun.

...Radio news gives you headlines in the shower and traffic reports on the freeway. Newspapers offer you national and local news and help you keep up with the latest, magazine describe new video games and keep you current with the latest fashion trends, social media headway through the tray of schedules, Shirley (2001, p.19) The Writer further notes that, adult spends more time more than half their waking lives with the media—more time than they spend sleeping. During the day, the average person spends more time with the media than without them.

Concept of News Framing

Framing is the process by which communication sources, such as news organizations, define and construct a political issue of public controversy. (Opata, 2017), views framing as part of a skill used in producing effects or understanding a certain issue. When an event is presented through a certain frame, it creates a type of meaning. Framing, therefore, refers to mass media capacity in choosing and stressing aspects of reality or event, till it becomes important. Sometimes, this is done to the extent of affecting public opinions.

Therefore, News framing suggests that the way and manner news is presented, influences the way it will be perceived and subsequently the decisions and choices that people will make. It refers to the way media gatekeepers organize and present events and

issues they cover and the way audiences interpret what they are provided with. To some scholars "a frame is a central organizing idea for news that supports a context and suggests what the issue is through the use of selection, emphasis, exclusion, and elaboration (Entman, 2015), framing essentially involves selection and salience.

To frame, it means to select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment for the item described.

Concept of Reportage

Reportage is the coverage of news and other events of general interest for newspapers, television, radio, and the internet (New Media). Most reporters file information or write their stories electronically from remote locations. In many cases, breaking stories are written by staff members, through information collected and submitted by other reporters who are out on the field gathering information for an event that has just occurred and needs to be broadcast instantly. "Radio and television reporters often compose stories and report "live" from the scene, (Sheyigari, 2019). Some journalists also interpret the news or offer opinions and analysis to readers, viewers, or listeners. In this role, they are called commentators or columnists.

Reporters take notes and also take photographs or shoot videos, either on their own, by citizens, or through a photographer or camera person. In the second phase, they organize the material, determine the focus or emphasis (identify the peg), and finally write their stories. The story is then edited by news or copy-editors. The headline of the story is

decided by the news desk, and practically never by the reporter or the writer of the piece. Often, the news desk also heavily re-writes or changes the style and tone of the first draft prepared by the reporter/writer originally. Ultimately, a collection of stories that have been picked for the newspaper or magazine edition, are laid out on dummy (trial) pages, and after the chief editor has approved the content, style, and language in the material, it is sent for publishing. The writer is given a byline for the piece that is published; his or her name appears alongside the article. This process takes place according to the frequency of the publication. News can be published in a variety of formats (broadsheet, tabloid, magazine, and periodical publications) as well as periods (daily, weekly, and semi-weekly, fortnightly, or monthly).

Concept of Insurgency

Remi (2017, p.34) conceptualize insurgency (or internal war) as: "a general overarching concept that refers to a conflict between a government and an out-group or opponent in which the latter uses both political resources and violence to change, reformulate, or uphold the legitimacy of one or more of four key aspects of politics" The scholar posited that, modern insurgencies have evolved from early political failures. While the presence of popular insurrections has been in the movement since early political form, their ability to achieve desired results has been minimal. According to Tankard (2019, p.45), "insurgencies have failed, or in any case have produced only limited victories, because the techniques they can exploit today were then irrelevant to the historical situation. "Insurgencies are not new in the history of states (Bakere, 2014), around the globe, the insurgency has sadly become one of the defining features of our society

today they go back to times of antiquity, as far back as the old civilizations of the Greek city-states and the Roman Empire when the rulers of these ancient civilizations often had to face the challenge of insurgencies, insurrections, and revolts. In modern history, examples of insurgencies and terrorism go back to at least four centuries, spanning many continents and states. "These include the French revolution of 1789 that replaced the Bourbon monarchy with the new French Republic, and the 1776 American war of independence from British colonial rule, Bakere (2014, p. 67)."

Literature Review

The media globally are no strangers to the coverage and reporting of crises including terrorism. Of course, their surveillance role in society bestows on them the obligation to watch events as they unfold and aptly report back to the society to enable the process of informed formulation of opinions and decisions, the sequel the name - watchdog of the society. "Media audience sees the world through the eye of the media" Rocho (2019, p.56). This is why many have studied how the media have carried out this all-important duty with keen interest and have reported a vibrant symbiotic interaction between both. News thrives in oddity, happenstances in the society including the erosion of peace and tranquility are the most sort after by newsmen because of the overt inherent reward for the media organization which include higher ratings and viewership, higher advertising patronage as a result of an increase in audience and of course every media organization will want to be the daring one who brings in the scoops.

In examining the role of the media in reporting conflicts, Freedman (2016, p.18) observed that "the media played more of the

role of sectional follow dog than a watchdog," citing the role of the media in the US-Vietnam war where the media was indicted of excluding important information that would have steered the war towards peace a long time before the war ended. According to Freeman (2016, p.45)," the exclusion include the voice of the anti-war movement in the US, the motives of the Vietnamese people and the inexpressible' notion that the US and not North Vietnam are the offenders," further noting that news that runs counter official during crises are deemed unfit for publication because the media is seen as always throwing their weight behind the government troops by framing the opposition in the worst light possible and muffling their voices, thereby distorting the public cognition.

Many media scholars have conducted studies to evaluate the nature, pattern, and effects of media coverage of Boko Haram activities and the government's response to the insurgency. (Okali, 2017) investigated newspaper coverage of Boko Haram attacks in Nigeria, to identify the frames in the stories published. A total of 120 editions of four selected newspapers were analyzed, his findings showed that straight news was predominant. The ineffective response of the government, in terms of its uncompromising behavior and inability to contain the insurgency, was widely reported. The findings also indicated that the newspapers dwelt so much inflammatorily on the impact of attacks by the sect and de-emphasized messages that could help end the violence. This is a clear example of the war journalism approach.

A related study, (Nwanne, 2015) did a content analysis of pictorial framing of the Boko Haram insurgency by The Daily Trust and The Nation newspapers, covering January 1st, 2011 to December 30, 2014. A total of

367 pictures on Boko Haram were generated from the 288 issues selected. The result showed that horrible themes constitute most pictures (61.4%) of Boko Haram. The study also found that most of the pictures could not communicate meanings to the readers without words.

(Odigbo, 2015) conducted a study to comparatively evaluate the framing of the government's response to Boko Haram insurgency over three years (2012-2014) on the YouTube webcast channels of Aljazeera, Cable Network News (CNN), and Channels Television. Adopting the content analysis research design, 157 videos were purposively sampled and analyzed using a validated coding sheet and manual subject Cohen Kappa's inter-coder reliability test which revealed an almost perfect agreement (Kappa= Coder 1, 2 & 3: 0.9997, 0.997, and 0.818). Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings revealed that all three international televisions gave prominence to the government's response to Boko Haram insurgency through its Security Agency Operations at 46% on Aljazeera, 36.5% on Channels, and 48.4% on CNN, while the analysis of the yearly trend in their framing presented a significant difference. Aljazeera and CNN adopted a more critical approach in their discourse, while Channels was mostly Distance.

However, (Nwaffor, 2016) investigated Nigerian Print media reportage of terrorism with a focus on Boko Haram activities. Three newspapers (The Punch, Daily Sun, and The Guardian) were used in the study. Considering the media frames investigated in the study, 42.0% was in favor of rescue efforts, hopelessness was recorded low with 2.3% and conspiracy frame was

1.1%. The study also found that terror prevention and intelligent gathering were more reported as urgent actions that government needs to take. Similarly, (Tankard, 2019) investigated "Foreign Media Coverage of Communal Conflicts in Nigeria: Implications for Effective Conflict Management". The study holds that negative foreign media report of conflict in Nigeria tends to make the parties to the conflict not to work towards an amicable resolution of the conflict. It cited the Jos as an example where many Western media, including CNN, VOA, and BBC reported that the endemic Jos crisis is religious. The study argued that such reports came at a time when major stakeholders in the crisis had openly said that the perpetrators of the crisis were hiding under religion to cause violence. Such a report by foreign media tends to aggravate the situation, considering the volatility and sensitivity of religious issues in Nigeria. It also holds that the gory pictures of casualties carried by foreign media about conflicts in Nigeria can easily incite parties to a conflict to embark on reprisal attacks. When such gory pictures and negative reports that follow are not balanced, the matter becomes even worse. By focusing more on conflict casualties, and less on efforts at curtailing the conflict, foreign media do not contribute to the conflict management mechanism, which they are supposed to do as a matter of corporate social responsibility.

While (Udoudo, 2015) examined the pattern of frames adopted by Nigerian newspapers in the coverage of the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria using the Guardian, Daily Sun, Vanguard, and ThisDay newspapers as test cases. The study found out that there are contrasting patterns in the frames used by the newspapers in coverage of Boko Haram in the year under study. The Guardian, Vanguard, and ThisDay newspapers

emphasized the responsibility frame 24% as against 17.1% emphasized by the Daily Sun newspaper. Also, among the 10 frames used as a yardstick for measuring newspaper coverage of the Boko Haram Insurgency, the dominant frame identified in the coverage was the Response frame, 26.3%. Findings also showed that there was 40% non-prevalence in the use of the frames.

In a bid to determine how advocacy journalism could conduce to the containment of Boko Haram terrorism and threat to national unity, (Obi, 2012) conducted a case study investigation into documents, diaries, journals, historical artifacts, newspapers/magazines, as well as broadcast media reports on Boko Haram terrorists' activities. The study found that the mainstream media by their very constitution, proprietorship, mode of operation, and sustenance in this economy do not have the luxury of time for analytical reports or patience for investigative reporting. They (mainstream media) therefore pander more to straight-jacketed reporting without much effort at embellishments.

The news is given flat and straight with objectivity as the watchword. At times, snippets of sensationalism are found. This is evidenced by the kind of headlines that stream across our regular daily, weeklies, and on the radio. The study argued that "the survival instinct could have contributed to this method of straight jacket reporting against other forms like advocacy journalism. Obi (2012, p.69).

It also held that the "success" of Boko-Haram correlates with the identified mode of journalistic reporting. The fulcrum of the study is that the media play a significant role in building perception.

Lawrence & Obayi (2018) tried to find out how the mass media could be optimally used to curtail the menace of the Boko Haram sect and by extension, preserve freedom of speech/other related freedoms; they contend that despite coming under attacks by the Boko Haram sect, Nigerian's mass media could still help in building positive and courageous attitudes in the people, in response to the sect's threats. According to the researchers, that could be done through the way the media frame their reports on Boko Haram's attacks, in respect of choice of words, pictures, and the language of the reports. The study concluded that Boko Haram is a faceless, conscienceless, and bloody bunch of mass-murdering terrorists and should be appropriately framed as such.

In their study on youths involvement in social conflicts and their implications on Nigeria's image, (Madike & Odigbo, 2014) came up with the following findings: that 34.21% of the respondents strongly agreed that there is a significant correlation between the Boko Haram crisis and Nigeria's international image, 48.42% equally agreed with that notion, whereas 6.58% of the respondents were not sure if there is any significant correlation; 5.53% and 5.26% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively.

(Dorcas, 2012) however, conducted a study on mass media and conflicts in Northern Nigeria. In that study which involved a content analysis of ThisDay, Guardian, and Tribune newspapers found that the motivating factors behind subjective coverage of the understudied issues were tribalism and religion. It then concludes that there is abundant evidence that the media instigated and sustained conflict in Northern Nigeria. It also submitted that the media also undoubtedly violated the laws and ethics of

media practice, and by such violations, committed a crime against the North and generality of the people of Nigeria.

In another study on audience perception of the role of the mass media in the coverage of the 2001 Tiv/Jukun ethnic conflict, Orhewere & Kur (2017) found that there is a tendency for the media to present the news quickly rather than accurately in crises and that early media reports of an unexpected event will tend to exaggerate the crisis. It, however, maintained that responsible media practice in times of conflict suggests that the media do not carry inaccuracies, distortions, conflict, confusion, and errors of facts in their reports; instead, the most crucial role of the media should be in helping to prevent or at least attenuate the severity of conflicts. It submits that the desire to report news quickly should not take overriding precedence over the accuracy, and advised the media to avoid stereotyping but focus more on the mechanisms of conflict management than on actual conflicts.

Insurgency: A Threat to National Security

Some reputable scholars have asserted that insurgency has and will continue to be a threat to any nation. Sequel to this assertion, Aduku & Benjamin, (2019) in their article "Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria" Implications for national security and restorative justice advance that the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria poses major security threats to the lives and property of the citizens, consequently affecting the socio-economic development of the nation. It is often argued that the causes of the Boko Haram grievances cannot easily be identified. Some argued that Boko Haram is a set of disgruntled charlatans who do not have a clear-cut aim about their actions and inactions (Nwaffor 2016). Boko Haram's

insurgency is fueled by Nigeria's history, geopolitical structure, ethnoreligious composition, and socioeconomic disparities (Udoudo 2015). The insurgency of Boko Haram, which started as a weak, disorganized, loosely coordinated, and inchoate movement, mutated to pose serious threats to national security. It developed a capability for strategic power projection, strategic intelligence, and the building of wide-ranging linkages to subvert the state. Boko Haram's proficiency in explosives and operational tempo as well as its tactical sophistication and aggressiveness have become a source of concern to many observers (Uyo, 2017). The group has also become more vicious and daring in methods, the scale of attacks, geographical reach, and selection of targets. Government offices, places of worship, media establishments, security forces buildings, private companies, and national and international institutions have been targeted by the group. In August 2011 they even launched a devastating attack on the United Nations Headquarters building in Abuja.

According to Remi (2017), the Boko Haram insurgency has security implications not only within Nigeria but also in neighboring countries and the regional and even the international environment. The resultant public security volatility in the region has been an impediment to trade and investment, peaceful co-existence and stability, as well as sustainable livelihood and development (Okoli, 2017). Moreover, the reach and operational capabilities of the group called Boko Haram is still growing, and it is beginning to be linked and supported with like-minded terrorist groups within the region and in the Sahel. This increasing transnational dimension provides an avenue for it to improve its capacity for more deadly attacks on a large scale that could continually pose a

serious threat to security and stability in the wider African continent. At the same time, such external terrorist groups are spreading their activities and influence. There is a southward movement of terrorists, especially members of Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM), through the Sahel towards Mali, Mauritania, and Niger and, more importantly, Nigeria, and this will have severe implications on national security and stability in West Africa (Oputa, 2017).

It should be noted, however, that the persistent threat is not only against security but also against socio-economic development. The violent activities of Boko Haram have threatened, weakened, and brought a serious paralysis to business, the banking sector, markets, tourism, the transport system, hospitality, internal and external investment, companies, and other economic activities. According to (Dorcas, 2017), due to attacks on banks, markets, parks, and government ministries, departments, and parastatals in northern Nigeria, human capital and investors are on the verge of collapsing. In a similar similar manner, people have migrated to other parts of the country. Economic backwardness, poverty, unemployment, insecurity, and failure in sustainable human capital development have increased, not only in the northern part but in the entire country as well as neighboring countries like Chad, Cameroon, Niger, and Benin.

Evaluation of Conflict Frames

This segment evaluates the manifest conflict frames in communicated texts using content analysis coding schema ranging from Hate Speeches to the use of militarized vocabulary are used to assess how many reports conform with the conflict framing of news reporting. To aid our comprehension of

how the reports are evaluated under this schema, a quick explanation is offered about the subunits. The ten subunits used and their working explanation according to Adamu (2014, p.27) is offered as:

- **Hate Speech-** an expression of hatred, resentment, and our disdain for the other side of the conflict.
- **Our enemy/threat to us-** expressions presenting the other as a threat and enemy to the interest of the other and hence must be dealt with
- **Prejudiced-** An expression of bias preventing objective considerations to an issue or event; usually with the opinion being one-sided.
- **Bad/good tagging-** referring to either side of the conflict as bad/good which equals name-calling.
- **War oriented-** reporting events thriving on oddities depicting war and violence
- **Accused the other-** reporting events with expressions that point accusing finger on a particular side of the conflict as being the bad spot
- **Who threw the stone first-** reports that thrives on blame game on a party of the conflict while exonerating the other of guilt
- **Us/Them-** reports conflicts from a dichotomized stance of Us (for) or Them(against)
- **Uses Militarized vocabulary-** employs military words in describing violence and situations which could douse the true meaning of the situation or heightens fears and apprehension in the polity.

Evaluation of Report Types

Some types of media content have been listed in a coding schema to help sort our reports into a typified report. Okey-Ogueji, (2016, p.71) enumerated some of the

types and how they are applied in this report are:

- **News reports-** strictly news content relayed by an in-house reporter who served as an eyewitness that covered the beat.
- **In-house program-** produced by the media on which some newsworthy discoveries were made, maybe by the ideas of interviewees or experts on the program
- **In-house documentary-** an in-depth investigative special report packaged by a media house that provides background information on a topical issue. It is characterized by various contributions from a woman on the street
- **Sponsored reports-** this includes all paid reports on a given issue.
- **Features reports-** similar to documentary reports lack the seriousness of documentary. It softens the news with various anecdotes.
- **Magazine programs-** this sort of program combines various forms of reports and presentation style. News reports can be culled from the proceeds of such programs.

Pitfalls of Framing Conflicts

As communication scholars continue to delve into the research of how the framing tool kit has been used to restructure political communication and steered public opinion towards the desired direction, certain limitations have been noted on the efficacy of the framing effect. For example, Okey-Ogueji, (2016) avers that frame tool is used in influencing public opinion. He also noted that selective exposure to elite frames is concomitant to whether frames mislead or misinform the audience as the latter had ab initio delegated credibility to elitist views and

consequently are dependent on them to make an informed opinion. This presents framing as being subjective rather than objective. This could be detrimental in a conflict situation because information about causes and resolution of the conflict may be permuted in a disjointed form, distorting both the understanding of the conflict and a possible move for peace.

Again, frames are operationalized with exposure to news stories. However, framing effects could be either minimized or submerged by other exposures to alternative sources such as local opinion leaders or two-step-flow of information which stipulates that mass media content first reaches opinion leaders, people who are active media users and who collect, interpret, and diffuse the meaning of media messages to less-active media consumers. In this case, the determination of framing effect is limited as it cannot be credited with being unbiased in opinion formation. The multi paradigmatic nature of framing and its association with other media persuasive tools as agenda setting and priming led Entman 2010 to have argued that the framing process is limited as a result of its scattered conceptualization which had impinged on it being developed into a paradigm.

However, this assertion had been debunked. Scholars who argued that the understanding and application of the framing process ought not to be one-way traffic rather the abundant accumulated knowledge that has been gathered by communication researchers over the years has led to a holistic understanding of frames and the framing process and eliminated fragmented findings (D'Angelo, 2002). The second theory supporting this study is the agenda-setting theory of the press. Though it has been

addressed as the mother of framing theory, their distinction was aptly mapped by (Weaver, 2007) who offered that agenda-setting is focused on the relative salience of issues or subjects, (while) the second level examines the relative salience of attributes of issues.

This simply means that agenda setting concerns itself in placing the importance of events by talking about them more and how events are talked about which is framing does. Shaw, (1979) assents to this as he wrote that the media, by describing and detailing what is out their present people with a list of what to think about and talk about. This holds when we consider the role of the media in a conflict situation. Usually, what is understood of a conflict; what is considered important, and what is left out in public opinion discussions about a conflict are all dependent on what the media have portrayed in their bulletins.

This theory is relevant to this study because of its opinion molding success. As discussed later in this chapter, Nigerian media have applied agenda-setting to effect attitude change in the face of epidemic health challenges and political communication. The position of peace journalism in effecting attitude change inclining toward peaceful resolutions could be attained with anchorage on agenda-setting.

Theoretical framework

This study adopted the framing theory of Mass Communication by Gregory Beston in 1972, which states that framing is sometimes referred to as second-level agenda settings because of its close relation to Agenda Seething Theory.

Framing Theory

The concept and theory of framing suggest that the way and manner an issue is

presented influences the way it will be perceived and subsequently the decisions and choices that people will make. It refers to the way media gatekeepers organize and present events and issues they cover and the way audiences interpret what they are provided with. To McQuail (2010, p.5) "a frame is a central organizing idea for news that supports a context and suggests what the issue is through the use of selection, emphasis, exclusion, and elaboration. In the words of (Entman 2017), framing essentially involves selection and salience. To frame therefore is to select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text, in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment for the item described. Several studies are in agreement that news is a construction by journalists, from a selection of occurrences. These studies submit that news is a social product molded by many organizational and professional factors. The underlying assumption of framing theory is that:

...determination of what is or not news, what is or is not significant, is a function not of the nature of the world "out there" but of the work of those who must somehow bring into being some things which are more important than others and hence, more worthy of publication, Entman (2015, p.56).

The way journalists do their work by selecting and processing what becomes news is not a neutral activity, as proponents of objectivity would like us to believe. Journalists are not dry wool that absorbs any liquid dipped into it. They (journalists) bring to their work certain knowledge or cultural maps

which in some way, influence the way they conceptualize events and issues.

Through the use of those frames, the press can "impose its meaning, frames, and symbols to a given event" Madike (2015, p.20). Through framing, journalists can organize otherwise fragmentary items and give them some structures to make them meaningful. In that context, (Mc Quail 2010) submits that framing is a way of giving some interpretation. On that note, one may reasonably ask, is there any possibility that journalists using different frames may signal the same event differently? The answer to this question is that it is rare for journalists to use different frames to signal the same event differently. This is because journalists seem to approach the same events using very similar frames. No wonder why Dunwoody and Griffin (2013, p.24) aver that "frames utilized by journalists for story construction are not idiosyncratic. Rather journalists across a wide range of media seem to employ similar mental maps and, thus produce stories that similarly reconstitute the world".

The framing theory is relevant to this study because Boko Haram is a shadowy but powerful sect, bent on enthroning its parochial religious belief in North/East Nigeria and by extension, the entire country. Again, the mass media can contribute immensely in the containment and ultimately, the defeat of the sect by the way they frame stories of the sect and its activities. In that regard, it becomes imperative that care should be taken in the choice of words, pictures, and language of the reports.

Conclusion

The usage of descriptive headlines that talk about the event, quotation, and comment headlines report what others said all blanketed the true position of the media.

This situates, the media outside the happenstances occurring in their environment. How objective a journalist can be in reporting a loss of lives that could as well be family or friends is yet to be established. But in the interim, the media need to situate themselves as responsible tools of either construction or destruction—there is no room for standing on the fence.

While expectations are high on how the media can assist the governments in less developed countries to obtain and retain democratic rule and keep public servants from embezzling public funds, all these may not be achievable if the polity is constantly being heated up as a result of framing conflict issues wrongly. Analogically, when there is a fire outbreak, the fire service comes to put it off with a tank of water, not petrol! To apply conflict frames in an already volatile situation would be an attempt by the media to escalate the problems. The media is the hope of the common person to be heard so have to fill in the gap adequately.

Conspicuously, there is a need for the Nigerian media to retrace their steps and align completely with the principles of peace journalism. Boko Haram insurgency is still ongoing with trends turning more dangerous than when it first started. It is not too late to apply the right tool in combating the insurgency. It will be of benefit to remember always that journalists are also soldiers fighting in every battle our society is faced with.

There is a feeling that the press in particular is not showing respect for the plural nature of the Nigerian cultural environment. However, in times of peace, people depend on the media as their source of information, but they depend on the media more in times of conflict. Also, the rumor mills are more

active in times of conflict than in peacetime. These two scenarios underscore the role of the media in conflict and peace management. Conflict is an indication of disagreement and the media handling it will go a long way in explaining the situation to resolve the conflict or aggravate the situation. The media must ensure the authenticity of the information being disseminated and convince the audience of the reality of the messages. The media has been seen or suspected of being involved in propaganda which in turn erodes its credibility.

A journalist should be encouraged in reporting terror-related news stories positively (emphasizing policy actions and response to the situation) especially when it is proven that the government is channeling effort in such direction. This has the benefit of causing the polity to trust the government in times of insecurity and uncertainty.

It is suggested that further studies could be carried out to include more framing categories and other forms of media to provide a more robust and comprehensive understanding of how the media covered an issue.

Suggestions

Given the discussions above, the media should ensure that:

- i. The feelings of the people of the North-East are properly reported irrespective of the feelings of the government and economic interest of the Media owners.
- ii. While it is important to put into consideration the interest of the Media owners of the various media houses, such interests should not override the ethics of the profession and the general national interest.
- iii. Similarly, the media should dedicate attention to reporting conflict and

insurgencies especially as it relates to using such reports to create peace rather than aggravate the situation.

- iv. The media must work in collaboration with stakeholders in the North East to ensure that government policies directed at curbing the conflicts are properly implemented.
- v. The media should refrain from giving any particular segment preference above the other.
- vi. The media should emphasize information that neutralizes friction and clear the ignorance and misconceptions which breed the Boko Haram insurgence.

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